

This questionnaire is one of the results of the doctoral thesis of Alién García-Hernández "Design and evaluation of the impact of an e-textbook in the engagement towards the learning of Discrete Mathematics learning", under the supervision of Teresa González-Ramírez, full professor at the University of Seville. Public grant from the Asociación Universitaria Iberoamericana de Posgrado (AUIP), the Universidad de Sevilla (Spain) and the Universidad de las Ciencias Informáticas (Cuba). The process of construction and validation of the questionnaire can be found in the article "Design and Validation of a Questionnaire to Assess Student Satisfaction with Mathematics Study Materials" published in open access. the access reference to the article is at the bottom of this page.

My mathematics study materials:

1 = Strongly disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Somewhat disagree, 4 = Neither agree or disagree, 5 = me what agree, 6 = Agree, 7= Strongly agree

<i>Didactic adequacy of mathematics study materials</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Conceptual summaries by content blocks	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Present mathematic contents in a pleasant way, showing their origin and evolution	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Sufficient variety of exercises for my study	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Adapted to the subjects' objectives and contents	<input type="checkbox"/>						
The level of difficulty of theoretical contents is in accordance with my studies	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Accurate progression of exercises regarding complexity	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Describe algorithms step by step to understand mathematic contents	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Sufficient exemplification of mathematic definitions, theorems and postulates	<input type="checkbox"/>						
<i>Motivational capacity of mathematics study materials</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Stimulate search and discovery	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Connected with my interests through educational motivation activities, such as puzzles, riddles, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Activities that promote game-based learning (gamification)	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Contents linked to my degree/studies/major	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Make visible the link between mathematic contents and real world	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Adapted to my social and cultural reality	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Helpful in my academic exams	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Foster a feeling of wellbeing in the study of mathematics	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Contribute to a better learning of the subject	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Easy to understand and connected to my interests	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Help to forget how difficult mathematics are	<input type="checkbox"/>						
<i>Overall quality of mathematics study materials</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
It is possible to ask the author and receive his/her answers	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Permit automatic self-evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Adjusted to my speed of learning	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Permit interaction with teachers and classmates	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Contents are updated every so often	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Equipped with audio-visual resources	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Accessible in mobile format	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Attractive graphic design that encourages learning	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Support the ideas or concepts developed in the text through illustrations or figures	<input type="checkbox"/>						

Contextual data

Gender: Female Male **Age:** **Class Group:** **Option in which you applied for your degree:**